

A Conductance-Based Design Methodology for Single-Transistor Organic Electrochemical Neurons

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Abstract—Organic electrochemical transistors (OECTs) combine ionic and electronic transport in a single device, exhibiting dynamics that closely resemble those of biological neurons. Their intrinsic plasticity, alongside low-voltage and low-energy operation, positions them as promising candidates for hardware-level neural emulation. Notably, the conjugated polymer poly(benzimidazobenzophenanthroline) (BBL) enables the realization of a spiking neuron within only one transistor. This configuration leverages BBL’s ion-dependent response times and antiambipolar transfer characteristics to produce the non-monotonic transconductance necessary to emulate action potentials. However, a unified model accounting for the combined effects of device geometry, input stimulus, and supply voltage on neural dynamics is currently lacking, constraining their systematic use in neuromorphic systems. To address this gap, we introduce a conductance-based design methodology for single-transistor organic electrochemical neurons (ST-OECNs). By decoupling drain current into carrier velocity and charge density, the framework captures critical multi-timescale dynamics, successfully replicating the subthreshold and suprathreshold spiking regimes observed in physical devices. Furthermore, the model reveals that scaling down channel length and thickness increases oscillation frequencies into biologically relevant regimes, while channel width tunes the operating stimulus range. Ultimately, the framework leverages these geometric relationships to inform device sizing for system integration, reducing the reliance on trial-and-error fabrication loops.

Index Terms—Organic electrochemical transistor, Organic electrochemical neuron, Conductance-based model, Neuromorphic

I. INTRODUCTION

The organic electrochemical transistor (OECT) has emerged as a highly promising candidate for next-generation bioelectronics and neuromorphic computing [1]. At their core, OECTs operate via ion-driven doping within organic mixed ionic-electronic conductors (OMIECs), modulating the carrier concentration and, consequently, the conductivity throughout the entire channel [2]. The volumetric charging mechanism endows OECTs with high transconductance and remarkable signal amplification capabilities [3], [4]. Furthermore, the inherent material properties of OMIECs provide OECTs with high biocompatibility, sub-volt operation, and high conformability and flexibility [5].

This work has been partially funded by the the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation program under grant agreement Nr 101135241 (BIOSENSEI) and by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 (GREENPATCH).

Since their internal ion transport dynamics closely resemble the ion-driven processes of biological neural and synaptic activity, OECTs have been widely adapted as both artificial synapses [6] and organic electrochemical neurons (OECNs) [11]–[13]. Operating as synapses, they successfully emulate short-term plasticity (STP) [7] and long-term plasticity (LTP) [8]–[10]. Meanwhile, at the cellular level, these artificial neurons actively mimic complex neuronal behaviors while responding to electrical and chemical stimulus. Recently, Ji et al. introduced a novel single-transistor OECN (ST-OECN) capable of emulate 17 distinct neural features without additional passive components [14]. This enables high-density integration of neurons, promoting the development of compact, robust, low-power hardware platforms for decentralized, brain-inspired sensory processing. However, a unified model that simultaneously relates the geometry, input stimulus, and supply voltage of the device to the resulting neural dynamics remains elusive, which limits the systematic integration of these devices into large-scale neuromorphic systems.

In this study, we propose a conductance-based methodology to design ST-OECNs. Using the OECT’s design parameters, we can predict its spiking behavior and operating ranges. Our approach involves dividing drain current into two components, each evolving on a different timescale in response to an external stimulus. When considering the acceleration effect that occurs during transitions between different doping states, two categories of spiking are identified: subthreshold and suprathreshold. The simulations demonstrate dynamics analogous to those of the actual device and expose the impact of channel dimensions on spiking behavior.

II. DEVICE DESCRIPTION

The ST-OECN consists of a single OECT based on poly(benzimidazobenzophenanthroline) (BBL) using an electrolyte containing protic cations, such as NH_4Cl (Fig. 1). The generation of action potentials relies on two characteristics: antiambipolar transfer characteristics and asymmetric transients. The transfer characteristics of the BBL-OECT at different drain potentials V_{DS} are shown in Fig. 2. It differs from a traditional n-type accumulation-mode OECT in that the current does not continue to increase linearly (beyond the saturation region) with respect to the gate potential V_{GS} . Instead, the

Fig. 1. Schematic of BBL-OECT showing the source (S), drain (D), gate (G) and electrolyte.

Fig. 2. Antiambipolar transfer characteristics of a BBL-OECT measured under different drain voltages (V_{DS})

transconductance decays past the drain current peak at V_p , eventually driving the device into a deactivated state matching the initial conductivity of the polymer. This behavior stems from severe ion accumulation; while it enhances the charge capacity of the material, it simultaneously degrades carrier mobility. Consequently, the BBL-OECT exhibits a single conductivity window that expands with increasing V_{DS} .

Due to this antiambipolar behavior, the BBL-OECT exhibits two distinct off-states: an undoped state characterized by ion deficiency, and a fully doped state resulting from ion saturation. Upon activation, the response time from the fully doped state is more than 1000 times slower than from the undoped state when using NH_4Cl as the electrolyte.

III. ST-OECN MODEL DESIGN

A. Conductance-based model

We represent the excitable membrane through the equivalent RC circuit shown in Fig. 3. Its capacitance is a fixed value that depends on the channel dimensions and the intrinsic capacitance of the material, whilst its resistance is the channel's conductance. The current flowing through the channel i_d varies as a function of the potential between the drain and the source v . The behavior of the circuit follows Kirchhoff's laws:

Fig. 3. Electrical equivalent of the excitable membrane: Parallel RC circuit with voltage-dependent resistance

Fig. 4. Drain characteristics of BBL-OECT at fixed V_{GS} . Due to its antiambipolar characteristic, I_D does not increase as soon as V_{DS} rises, but only after a threshold voltage is reached. Once the pinch-off voltage V_p is achieved, the BBL-OECT transitions from the high-doped state to the low-doped state, reducing the current response time.

$$C\dot{v} = -i_d(v) + i_{app} \quad (1)$$

We can define a time constant $\tau_m = R_{ch}C$ for the voltage equation, where R_{ch} is the resistance of the channel at the equilibrium point.

$$\tau_m \dot{v} = R_{ch}(-i_d(v) + i_{app}) \quad (2)$$

Given the antiambipolar characteristics of the BBL-OECT, the steady-state current does not follow the output curve of a traditional OECT. Instead, it resembles a curve as shown in Fig. 4, with high resistance at low potentials and saturation at high voltages. The current can be analyzed one-dimensionally in terms of two distinct components: the carrier velocity ν , and the charge density n .

$$i_d(v, n) = \nu(v) \cdot n \quad (3)$$

$$\nu(v) = \frac{\mu_0 \frac{v}{L} + \nu_{sat} \left(\frac{v}{V_0} \right)^4}{1 + \left(\frac{v}{V_0} \right)^4} \quad (4)$$

$$\tau_s \dot{n} = n_0(v) - n \quad (5)$$

$$n_0(v) = \frac{\beta}{1 + \exp(-\alpha(v - V_n))} \quad (6)$$

The function $\nu(v)$ relates the carrier velocity to the drain-source potential. This is the Hilsum-Rees/Barnes formula, an analytical model used in semiconductor physics to capture the velocity-field characteristics of materials exhibiting negative differential mobility. At low electric fields, the fourth-power scaling terms approach zero, reducing the expression to Ohm's linear relation, which is governed by low-field mobility and channel distance μ_0/L . At intermediate values near V_0 , the shifting mathematical weight creates an inflection point where the curve peaks and then decreases with a negative slope. Finally, at high values ($v \gg V_0$), the fourth-power terms dominate and cancel out the other variables, forcing the function to flatten horizontally and asymptotically lock into a constant value ($\nu \approx \nu_{sat}$). This decline in carrier velocity can be attributed to the intense electric field pushing of electrons toward regions where the Coulomb gap has completely split the density of states [15]. Because the gap acts as an energetic void, the electrons literally run out of accessible empty states to hop into along that field vector. They become electrostatically blocked by the repulsion of the neighbors ahead of them.

The variable n links the carrier density to the drain/source potential whilst the BBL-OECT is in the high-doped state (HDS). At low voltages, the carrier density is very close to zero because the electric field is not strong enough to counteract the electrostatic force trapping the charges in place due to the intense Coulomb gap. Once some threshold voltage is reached, the carrier density begins to increase until its maximum value β . The parameter α controls the growth rate, while V_n is the potential where the conductivity is half the maximum. In OECTs, the charge density depends on the ions that enter the semiconductor from the electrolyte. This variable converges to the target value n_0 with a time constant τ_s greater than τ_m because the ionic mobility is significantly lower than that of the electronic carriers.

B. Firing and saturation

When the pinch-off voltage $V_p = V_{GS} - V_{th}$ is reached, the effective gate potential applied close to the drain terminal drops sharply. This expels surrounding ions, temporarily turning that area into an insulator. A sudden rise in the potential is required to maintain the injected current, akin to a trigger mechanism. At the same time, it transitions from HDS to low-doped state (LDS), accelerating the device's response. This effect is modeled by making a voltage-dependent time constant:

$$\tau_m = \tau_{HDS} - \frac{\tau_{LDS} - \tau_{HDS}}{1 + \exp(-k(v - V_p))} \quad (7)$$

where τ_{LDS} and τ_{HDS} are the time constants in the LDS and HDS respectively, and k is the rate of transition between these two states. Finally, the membrane voltage reaches the supply potential of the current source.

$$\tau_m \dot{v} = \begin{cases} R_{ch}(-i_d(v, n) + i_{app}) & \text{if } v < V_{dd} \\ \min(0, R_{ch}(-i_d(v, n) + i_{app})) & \text{if } v = V_{dd} \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

C. Device sizing relation

The channel resistance at the equilibrium point depends on the concentration of ions entering the channel as a function of the effective voltage applied to the semiconductor. Equation (9) allows R_{ch} to be calculated based on the channel width W , length L and thickness d :

$$R_{ch} = \frac{L}{ep\mu Wd} \quad (9)$$

where e is the charge of the electron, p is the charge density, and μ is the charge mobility. p is related to the number of ions entering the channel, being proportional to the effective voltage $V_{GS} - V_{th}$ and to the volumetric capacitance of the polymer C^* . V_{th} is the minimum V_{GS} potential required for ions move into the channel.

$$p = \frac{C^*(V_{GS} - V_{th})}{e} \quad (10)$$

$$R_{ch} = \frac{L}{C^*(V_{GS} - V_{th})\mu Wd} \quad (11)$$

Since the capacitance of the semiconductor is $C = C^*WdL$, where C^* is the volumetric capacitance of the BBL, the time constants τ_{LDS} and τ_{HDS} are obtained as follows:

$$\tau_{LDS} = \frac{L^2}{\mu_{LDS}(V_{GS} - V_{th})} \quad (12)$$

$$\tau_{HDS} = \frac{L^2}{\mu_{HDS}(V_{GS} - V_{th})} \quad (13)$$

The time constant τ_s indicates how quickly the ions respond to a change in the electric field. This parameter varies with the channel thickness d because the ions move perpendicular to the channel.

$$\tau_s = \frac{d^2}{\mu_{ion}(V_{GS} - V_{th})} \quad (14)$$

The saturation velocity is estimated as $\nu_{sat} = V_p\mu_{DS}/L$. The potential V_0 appears to depend on the maximum conductivity of the OECT, with a value between 0.2 and 0.3 V. Given that β is the maximum carrier density, this parameter is obtained by dividing the maximum current by the saturation velocity:

$$\beta = \frac{V_p}{\nu_{sat}R_{ch}} \quad (15)$$

Fig. 5. Experimental and modeled responses of the ST-OECN at subthreshold (a) and suprathreshold (b) spiking.

IV. SIMULATIONS

Table I lists the parameters used in the simulation of the results shown in Fig. 5 and 6. Three operating regimes are clearly displayed: at low stimulus levels, the neuron does not generate any spikes (silent). At slightly higher stimulus, the neuron transitions to tonic spiking with a voltage peak below the pinch-off voltage (subthreshold spiking). The voltage peak of the spikes depends on the level of the applied stimulus. If the stimulus is large enough to reach the pinch-off voltage, we transition to the third regime (suprathreshold spiking), where the potential rises very rapidly until it saturates at V_{dd} . The slow response causes the potential to drop back below the pinch-off voltage, returning to the HDS timescale, until the potential rises again and the cycle repeats. Fig. 5 compares the model's response with subthreshold and suprathreshold spiking measurements obtained from a device fabricated with the same dimensions.

TABLE I
SIMULATION PARAMETERS

Parameter	Symbol	Value
Channel width	W	400 μm
Channel length	L	50 μm
Channel thickness	d	50 nm
Volumetric capacitance	C^*	150 $\text{F} \cdot \text{cm}^{-3}$
Gate/source voltage	V_{GS}	0.45 V
Threshold voltage	V_{th}	-0.05 V
Crossover potential	V_0	0.27 V
Half-maximum conductance voltage	V_n	0.37 V
State transition steepness	k	100 V^{-1}
Carrier density growth rate	α	20
Charge mobility at high-doped state	μ_{HDS}	$6.3788 \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^2 \text{V}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$
Charge mobility at low-doped state	μ_{DS}	$4.3188 \times 10^{-3} \text{ cm}^2 \text{V}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$
Low-field charge mobility	μ_0	$1 \times 10^{-2} \text{ cm}^2 \text{V}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$
Ion mobility	μ_{ion}	$2.973 \times 10^{-12} \text{ cm}^2 \text{V}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$
Stimulus	i_{app}	3.2, 3.5 μA
Voltage supply	V_{dd}	1 V

ST-OECNs stand out for their ability to mimic many neural characteristics within a single device. The model reproduces many of these characteristics when evaluated with non-continuous stimulus. Fig. 6a and b show the relationship between the stimulus level and duration and the spike amplitude. Fig. 6c-f reproduce the neuronal characteristics of integration, refractoriness, resonance, and accommodation. These features are useful in neuromorphic chips because they facilitate to naturally handle time-dependent data, self-regulate their activity, and filter out noise without relying on massive, energy-hungry software algorithms.

Among the model parameters, we examined the effect of varying the channel dimensions in order to understand their effect on the scalability of the device. Figure 7 shows the peak frequency rate (PFR) during suprathreshold spiking and the stimulus required to reach this regime, varying one parameter at a time (OAT) while keeping all others at their default values (Table I). Although OAT analysis cannot capture interaction effects between parameters, it provides a first-order characterization to easily interpret parameter sensitivity.

Regarding the impact of width, the PFR remains entirely unchanged at approximately 1.21 Hz across a logarithmic scale ranging from 100 to 1000 μm . However, the stimulus required to reach this peak rate increases monotonically with width, rising from approximately 1.1 μA to 10 μA , suggesting that while firing frequency remains independent of width, energy demand scales with the size of the structure. For the top-gate configuration being considered, the independence of channel width from frequency is attributable to its irrelevance with respect to the movement of charges along the channel and the movement of ions in the thickness direction.

Moving to the length dimension, the results show a steady increase in frequency as the scale is reduced from 100 μm down to roughly 5 μm . At maximum length, the peak firing

Fig. 6. Model response at pulsed current stimulus: one spike (a) amplitude and (b) duration reaction, two spikes (c) integration, (d) refractoriness, (e) resonance and (f) accommodation.

Fig. 7. Peak firing rate and stimulus as function of channel dimensions

rate is at its lowest point of approximately 0.2 Hz , and as the length shortens, the firing rate climbs to nearly 2.2 Hz . Concerning stimuli, it follows roughly the same trend that the frequency—the shorter the channel length, the greater the current required. It ranges from about $1 \mu A$ at $100 \mu m$ to $13.5 \mu A$ at the shortest scale. Obviously, the shorter the distance the charges need to travel, the fastest the response to input current. On the other hand, shortening the channel length also increases conductivity. A stimulus that previously caused the neuron to spike above the threshold may no longer do so because it shifts the spiking threshold to voltage ranges below the crossover potential.

Finally, analyzing thickness from the largest scale ($1 \mu m$) to the smallest (10 nm) reveals the most extreme sensitivity in the model. At a thickness of $1 \mu m$, the peak firing rate is essentially zero, while the stimulus requirement is at its highest point of approximately $16 \mu A$. As the thickness is reduced, the firing rate experiences a massive recovery, surging to over 7 Hz at the 10 nm scale. Concurrently, the required current drops to approximately $1.5 \mu A$ for the thinnest films. This confirms minimizing thickness as a compelling strategy for achieving both high-frequency firing and low energy consumption.

Although slow ion transport typically limits the response time of OECTs, our model highlights a more nuanced geometric dependency. While reducing channel thickness accelerates ionic diffusion to enhance oscillation frequency, an excessively long channel introduces carrier transit limitations as a secondary bottleneck. This behavior suggests minimizing both channel length and thickness as a required strategy to maximize the device’s operating frequency. Meanwhile, modulating the channel width provides a straightforward lever to tailor the operational current levels of the artificial neuron.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This study demonstrates a conductance-based methodology that successfully bridges OECT design parameters with predictable spiking behavior in ST-OECNs. By decoupling the drain current into carriers velocity and charge density, the proposed framework captures the essential multi-timescale dynamics inherent to conductance-based neural models. By incorporating the voltage acceleration effect during the transition between doping states, the model replicated the two regimes of excitability (subthreshold and suprathreshold spiking) observed in devices fabricated with the same dimensions.

Besides closely mirroring the behavior of physical ST-OECN devices, our approach also displays the critical role that channel dimensions play in modulating spike characteristics. As the length and thickness of the channel decrease, the oscillation frequency increases. With microscale manufacturing techniques, frequencies in the tens of hertz can be achieved. The width of the channel can be used to adjust the range of stimulus within which the neuron operates.

Ultimately, this predictive framework provides hardware designers with a practical toolset to optimize ST-OECNs prior to fabrication. Future work will explore additional geometric factors influencing device behavior, including gate-channel distance, channel overlap, and lateral diffusion. Furthermore, we aim to refine the model through comprehensive empirical characterization across multiple devices and varied channel scales, establishing a definitive link between physical dimensions and complex spiking outputs.

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